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● On the genus *Jujiroa* Uéno, 1952 (Coleoptera: Carabidae: Platynini) from the Chinese mainland: a species overview to date, with description of a new species

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Abstract: All species of the genus *Jujiroa* Uéno, 1952 from the Chinese mainland are overviewed in this paper. A checklist with corresponding Chinese vernacular name and an updated key for identification are provided. Additionally, a new species from Mucheng Town, Jiajiang County, Sichuan Province is described and illustrated, and two species previously known only from a single sex are supplemented with descriptions of the opposite sex.

Keywords: China, ground beetles, Platyninae, taxonomy, new record

● 中国大陆穴胫步甲属（鞘翅目：步甲科：细胫步甲族）研究：现有物种概览及一新种描述

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摘要：本文对中国大陆分布的穴胫步甲属（*Jujiroa* Uéno, 1952）物种进行总体回顾，编写了含对应中文名的物种名录，并提供了更新后的物种鉴定检索表。此外，本文对采自四川省夹江县木城镇的一个新种进行形态描述与制图，同时为两个此前仅已知单性的物种补充了异性的形态描述。

关键词：中国，步甲，细胫步甲亚科，分类学，新记录

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● Introduction

The East Asian endemic genus *Jujiroa* belonging to the tribe Platynini was established by Uéno, 1952 based on the type species *Jujiroa nipponica* (Habu, 1950) from Ryugado, Japan. Currently, a total of 41 species have been described, of which 20 in China, 19 in Japan, two in Vietnam (Casale & Heinz 2000; Sasakawa 2006; Wada & Ashida 2022; Anichtchenko *et al.* 2026).

The known *Jujiroa* species from China are mainly concentrated in Sichuan and Taiwan Provinces, with ten and seven species respectively; the remaining five are distributed separately in Chongqing Municipality, Guangxi, Jiangxi, Shanxi, and Zhejiang Provinces. However, no complete checklist or identification key for these species has been published to date.

During a caving investigation in Jiayang County of Sichuan Province, one specimen morphologically consistent with the genus *Jujiroa* was collected. After careful examination in the laboratory, we can confirm that this adult represents a new species.

In view of the above, we provide an updated overview of the *Jujiroa* species from the Chinese mainland in this paper, including a checklist, an identification key, and a distribution map, in addition to the description and illustrations of a new species. Furthermore, two species previously known only from a single sex are supplemented with descriptions of the opposite sex.

● Material and methods

Morphological observations and the aedeagus dissection were conducted under a stereomicroscope (OlympusSZ2-ILST). Habitus, diagnostic features, as well as measurements were taken using a digital stereomicroscope (KEYENCE-VHX-5000). All images were finally modified and arranged to plate by Adobe Photoshop CC 2019.

Materials examined in this paper are deposited at the following institutions and personal collections:

CBFU — Beijing Forestry University, Beijing, China;

CNU — Chongqing Normal University, Chongqing, China;

SCAU — South China Agricultural University, Guangzhou, China;

CJCZ — collection of Jia-Cheng Zhang, Harbin, China;

CYZH — collection of Yu-Zhou Huang, Changsha, China.

Measurements and abbreviations are as follows: body length (**BL**) was measured from the apical margin of the clypeus to the elytral apices; head length (**HL**) was measured from the apical margin of the clypeus to the occipital constriction; head width (**HW**) was measured along the greatest width of head, along outer margins of eyes or tempora; pronotum width (**PW**) was measured along its greatest width; pronotum length (**PL**) was measured along its median line; Forebody length (**FbL**) is the sum of **HL** and **PL**; elytra length (**EL**) was measured from anterior margin to apices of the elytra; elytra width (**EW**) was measured along the widest part of both elytron combined; length of apical lamella (**AL**) was measured from apical margin of apical orifice to the extreme apex of median lobe; width of apical lamella (**AW**) was measured along base of apical lamella.

● Taxonomy

Genus *Jujiroa* Uéno, 1952 穴胫步甲属

Remarks. The genus *Jujiroa* was well defined previously (Uéno 1952; Jiang & Zeng 2025). It is obvious that *Jujiroa rainerschnelli* Lassalle, 2010 (type locality: Lao Cai, Vietnam) should be excluded from this genus, for the combinations of the following aspects: (1) dorsal surface with metallic luster; (2) eyes developed and hemispherical; (3) antennomere 3 distinctly curved; (4) submentum with only one pair of setae; (5) elytra with apical margins

obliquely and widely truncate. However, its generic placement remains uncertain due to limited material. It therefore needs to be treated as *incertae sedis* within the tribe Platynini until more material or molecular data become available for study. As for *Jujiroa suenisoni* Kirschenhofer, 1990 (type locality: Shanxi, China), Casale & Sciaky (1999) pointed out that its original description corresponds to that of *Pseudotaphoxenus* species and suggested a close relationship with *P. mongolicus* (Jedlička, 1953), therefore, we excluded it from the checklist as well.

Checklist of *Jujiroa* species from Chinese mainland

- J. clarkei* Deuve, 2004 [克氏穴胫步甲]; Guangxi: Lingyun County
J. danxue sp. n. [丹穴胫步甲]; Sichuan: Jiajiang County
J. deliciola Uéno & Kishimoto, 2001 [纤穴胫步甲]; Sichuan: Xingwen County
J. duqianae Tian & He, 2023 [杜倩穴胫步甲]; Sichuan: Shawan District
J. inexpectata Tian & Wang, 2020 [非望穴胫步甲]; Anhui: Huangshan District
J. iolandae Vigna Taglianti, 1995 [约氏穴胫步甲]; Sichuan: Huaying County-level City (type locality), Xuanhan County (new record); Chongqing: Beibei District (new record)
J. jinqiao Jiang, Zeng, Xue & Ma, 2026 [锦桥穴胫步甲]; Zhejiang: Suichang County
J. kusha Jiang, Zeng, Xue & Ma, 2026 [哭砂穴胫步甲]; Sichuan: Nanjiang County
J. lingguanensis Deuve & Pütz, 2013 [灵关穴胫步甲]; Sichuan: Baoxing County
J. maotiani Jiang & Zeng, 2025 [茂天穴胫步甲]; Chongqing: Banan District
J. rufescens (Jedlička, 1961) [红穴胫步甲]; Jiangxi: Guangxin District
J. satoi Uéno, 2007 [佐藤穴胫步甲]; Sichuan: Lushan County (type locality), Dayi County (Uéno 2007b)
J. uenoi Tian & He, 2020 [上野穴胫步甲]; Sichuan: Shawan District
J. wangzheni Tian & He, 2020 [王震穴胫步甲]; Sichuan: Gulin County
J. zhouchaoi Tian & He, 2020 [周超穴胫步甲]; Sichuan: Dujiangyan County-level City

Key to *Jujiroa* species from Chinese mainland

- 1 Body size larger, BL > 19.0 mm; elytral interval 3 with five setigerous pores...*J. lingguanensis* Deuve & Pütz
- Body size smaller, BL < 16.0 mm; elytral interval 3 with three setigerous pores at most.....2
- 2 Elytral striae with punctures quite coarse.....3
- Elytral striae impunctate, or just finely punctate.....4
- 3 Pronotum with lateral margin rather widely explanate, anterior angles narrowly angled, strongly projecting forward; elytra with parascutellar pore absent; elytral apices widely acute, hardly projecting.....*J. zhouchaoi* Tian & He
- Pronotum with lateral margin narrow, anterior angles widely rounded, weakly projecting; elytra with parascutellar pore present; elytral apices sharp and mucronate.....*J. wangzheni* Tian & He
- 4 Elytral interval 3 without setigerous pores, or with only one setigerous pore, usually near apex; elytral intervals 7–9 more or less sunken at about basal fourth.....5
- Elytral interval 3 with two or three setigerous pores, the distal pores distant from elytral apices, usually at apical third to fourth; elytral intervals 7–9 generally convex.....8
- 5 Eyes atrophic, almost indistinct; elytral interval 3 without setigerous pores.....*J. satoi* Uéno
- Eyes small and slightly convex; elytral interval 3 with one setigerous pore near apex.....6
- 6 Antennae relatively short, reaching the apical fifth of elytra; pronotum shorter than width, PL/PW 0.96; median lobe of aedeagus relatively stubby, with apical lamella shorter than width.....*J. duqianae* Tian & He

- Antennae longer, almost reaching the apical apices elytra; pronotum longer than width, PL/PW 1.05; median lobe of aedeagus slender, with apical lamella longer than width.....7
- 7 Forebody relatively robust, more elongate (FbL/EL > 0.70); pronotum with anterior angles rounded, slightly projecting forward; pronotal lateral margin sinuate at basal seventh; aedeagus with apical lamella distinctly bent to right side in dorsal view; Chongqing.....***J. maotiani* Jiang & Zeng**
- Forebody relatively delicate, shorter (FbL/EL < 0.67); pronotum with anterior angles obtuse, distinctly projecting forward; pronotal lateral margin nearly straight from basal third to posterior angles; aedeagus with apical portion straight; Sichuan.....***J. danxue* sp. n.**
- 8 Elytra with parascutellar pore absent.....9
- Elytra with parascutellar pore present.....10
- 9 Antennae very long, extending over elytral apices; pronotum longer than wide, with lateral margin less explanate, relatively narrow; tarsomeres with dorsal surface smooth; Sichuan...***J. deliciola* Uéno & Kishimoto**
- Antennae shorter, only reaching elytral middle; pronotum shorter than wide, with lateral margin widely explanate; tarsomeres with dorsal surface longitudinally sulcate; Jiangxi.....***J. rufescens* (Jedlička)**
- 10 Anterior angles of pronotum rounded, just slightly projecting; elytral apices with tips blunt, not mucronate; Guangxi.....***J. clarkei* Deuve**
- Anterior angles of pronotum distinctly projecting, narrowly obtuse or acute, usually angled; elytral apices with tips sharp, usually mucronate.....11
- 11 Forebody relatively shorter (FbL/EL < 0.67); elytral basal margin strongly sinuate at the joint with angular base of stria 1, forming acute angle with parascutellar striole; metacoxa trisetose, one inner setae present; elytral striae distinctly punctate; aedeagus with right paramere wider, similar to left paramere.....***J. uenoi* Tian & He**
- Forebody more robust and elongate (FbL/EL > 0.70); elytral basal margin nearly straight, forming obtuse angle with parascutellar striole; metacoxa bisetose, the inner setae absent; elytral striae impunctate, or with punctures quite fine; aedeagus with right paramere distinctly narrower than left paramere.....12
- 12 Antenna shorter, reaching apical fourth of elytra; pronotum with anterior angles acute; Eastern China.....13
- Antenna shorter, reaching apical fifth of elytra (except *J. kusha*); pronotum with anterior angles obtuse; Western China.....14
- 13 Submentum bisetose each side; pronotum with posterior margin straight, posterior angles not projecting backward; gonocoxite 2 of ovipositor longer and nearly straight; Anhui.....***J. inexpectata* Tian & Wang**
- Submentum trisetose each side; pronotum with posterior margin slightly curved, posterior angles slightly projecting backward; gonocoxite 2 of ovipositor shorter and curved; Zhejiang.....***J. jinqiaoi* Jiang, Zeng, Xue & Ma**
- 14 Eyes larger, distinctly convex; elytral striae impunctate; elytral interval 3 with three setigerous pores; aedeagus with apical lamella shorter, AL/AW 1.07, tips blunter in lateral view.....***J. kusha* Jiang, Zeng, Xue & Ma**
- Eyes smaller, slightly convex; elytral striae finely punctate; elytral interval 3 with two setigerous pores; aedeagus with apical lamella longer, AL/AW 1.60, tips sharp.....***J. iolandae* Vigna Taglianti**

***Jujiroa danxue* sp. nov.** 丹穴胫步甲

<https://zoobank.org/E58177DD-6E96-4379-BBCF-0D2188C1C111>

Figs 1, 2A–D, 4

FIGURE 1. *Jujiroa danxue* sp. n.: **A** habitus **B** mentum **C** pronotum **D** metacoxa **E** elytron; scale bars = 1.0 mm, white points: setigerous pores.

Type material. Holotype: ♂ (SCAU), labeled: “Pangpo Cave, Mucheng Town, Jiajiang County, Leshan City, Sichuan Province [四川省乐山市夹江县木城镇庞坡洞], 29.8030319°N, 103.43650559°E, h=534m, 2026.2.22, leg. Tian-Xuan Gu”.

Description. Body small-size and elongate, BL 12.6 mm; depigmented and dorsal surface concolorous brown (Fig. 1A).

Head elongate, longer than wide, HL/HW 1.36. Labrum with anterior margin bisinuate; six setae present. Frons flat, without punctures; frontal sulci shallow. Eyes small, almost not convex. Tempora slightly expanded laterally. Antennae long, reaching the apical eighth of elytra. Mentum with one pair of setae, mentum tooth bifid (Fig. 1B). Submentum with two setae on each side (Fig. 1B). Microsculpture isodiametric on frons, gradually turned to transverse to vertex.

Pronotum (Fig. 1C) nearly rectangular, PL/PW 1.05, widest at about apical third; both anterior and posterior margins straight; anterior angles obtuse, distinctly projecting forward; lateral margin slightly explanate, widely curved before middle, nearly straight from basal third to posterior angles, not sinuate before posterior angles;

posterior angles near right-angled, with tips blunt. Disc with median area smooth, area near anterior and lateral margins finely punctate and wrinkled. Basal foveae transverse, with basal sulcus distinct.

Elytra (Fig. 1E) elongate, EL/EW 1.83, widest just before middle; basal margin nearly straight, forming obtuse angle with parascutellar stria; shoulders rounded, without denticles. Striae finely punctate; parascutellar stria not joint to stria 1, stria 1 complete. Intervals commonly convex. Parascutellar pore present; interval 3 with only one setigerous pore at apical seventh, adjacent to stria 2; interval 7 with two or three preapical pores; umbilical pore series on interval 9 composed of approximately 19–20 pores. Apical apices acute and slightly mucronate.

Legs thin and slender; metacoxa bisetose, the inner setae absent (Fig. 1D); tarsi dorsally smooth, without longitudinal sulci.

FIGURE 2. Genitalia of *Jujiroa* spp.: **A–D** aedeagus of *J. danxue* sp. n. **E** gonocoxite 2 of ovipositor of *J. kusha* **F–I** aedeagus of *J. iolandae*; **A, F** median lobe in lateral view **B, G** right paramere **C, H** left paramere **D, I** median lobe in dorsal view; scale bars = 0.5 mm.

Male genitalia. Median lobe of aedeagus slender in lateral view (Fig. 2A), ventral margin evenly curved along the full length, apex weakly bent to the ventral side; apical lamella thick in lateral view; long and straight in dorsal view (Fig. 2D), AL/AW 1.51; apex with a narrow tip in both lateral and dorsal view. Right paramere narrow, apex narrowly rounded (Fig. 2B); left paramere wide, apex narrowly rounded (Fig. 2C).

Female genitalia. Unknown.

Diagnosis. BL 12.6 mm; depigmented and microphthalmic; forebody relatively delicate, short (FbL/EL < 0.67). Antennae long, reaching apical 1/8 of elytra; submentum bisetose at each side. Pronotum nearly rectangular, PL > PW; pronotum with anterior angles obtuse, distinctly projecting forward; lateral margin slightly explanate, nearly straight from basal third to posterior angles. Elytra with striae finely but distinctly punctate; interval 3 with only one setigerous pores at apical 1/7, interval 7 with two or three preapical pores, intervals 7–9 generally convex; elytral apical apices acute and slightly mucronate. Aedeagus with apical portion straight, apical lamella longer than its basal width.

Comparison. This new species is most similar with *J. duqianae* Tian & He, 2023 and *J. maotiani* Jiang & Zeng, 2025, they differ from others congener species by the combination of the following important aspects: (1) forebody relatively delicate and short; (2) pronotum with anterior angles obtuse, distinctly projecting forward; (3) pronotum with lateral margin slightly explanate; (4) elytral striae with punctures fine but distinct; (5) interval 3 with only one setigerous pores near apex; (6) intervals 7–9 generally convex, not sunken; (7) elytra with apical apices acute and slightly mucronate.

J. danxue sp. n. can be easily distinguished from *J. duqianae* by: (1) pronotum shape different, pronotum of the new species nearly rectangular, distinctly longer than width (PL/PW 1.05), lateral margin less curved (*vs. J. duqianae* with pronotum cordate, shorter than width, PL/PW 0.96, lateral margin strongly curved after anterior angles and distinctly sinuate before posterior angles); (2) elytral striae with punctures more distinct; (3) aedeagus with apical lamella longer, AL/AW 1.51 (*vs. AL/AW* 0.93 in *J. duqianae*). Compared to *J. maotiani*, the new species can be distinguished by: (1) Comparing with elytra, forebody relatively shorter, FbL/EL < 0.67 (*vs. relatively longer*, FbL/EL > 0.70 in *J. maotiani*); (2) pronotum with anterior angles obtuse, distinctly projecting forward (anterior angles widely rounded, just slightly projecting in the latter); (3) pronotal lateral margin nearly straight from basal third to posterior angles (*vs. distinctly sinuate* at basal seventh in *J. maotiani*); (4) the setigerous pore on interval 3 located at apical 1/7 (*vs. at apical* 1/5 in *J. maotiani*); (5) aedeagus with apical portion straight (*vs. apical lamella distinctly bent* to right side in dorsal view in *J. maotiani*).

This new species can also resemble *J. satoi* Uéno, 2007, a geographically close species. They share the characters of a nearly rectangular pronotum, elytral interval 3 without apical setigerous pores, and elytral intervals 7–9 generally convex, but the new species can readily be distinguished by: (1) eyes small but distinct, while eyes of *J. satoi* atrophic; (2) pronotum of *J. danxue* sp. n. distinctly longer than width, PL/PW 1.05, while shorter than width in *J. satoi*; (3) elytral interval 3 with one setigerous pore (*vs. without pores* in *J. satoi*); (4) median lobe of aedeagus slenderer.

Etymology. The scientific name of the new species is derived from “Dan Xue”, literally meaning “red cave”, which in ancient Chinese mythology is recorded as the birthplace of the Phoenix (Feng Huang) in the classic “Shan Hai Jing”. The type locality, Pangpo Cave, is traditionally said to be the hermitage of Pang Degong, the paternal elder of the Three Kingdoms strategist Pang Tong. It was Pang Degong who first coined the title “Young Phoenix” for Pang Tong. As a specific name, *danxue* thus weaves together the mythical origin of the phoenix, the literal red hue (Fig. 4A) of the cave entrance, and the historical legacy of the type locality.

Distribution. China: Sichuan Province, only known from the type locality, Mucheng Town of Jiajiang County (Fig. 6).

Habitat. (Fig. 4) The type locality, Pangpo Cave, is a sandstone cave situated at 543 m elevation. It has a north-facing entrance approximately 8 m high and 2 m wide (Fig. 4A), and remains moist year-round with running water and small pools. It is structured in three vertically connected layers. The main passage exits (Fig. 4B) on the south

side of the mountain, around 10 m higher than and only 80 m distant from the north entrance. Numerous narrow, impassable branch caves are present. The new species was discovered in a gravel pile about 15 m from the south exit (Fig. 4C). Other cavernicolous fauna observed include *Epanerchodus* sp. (Fig. 4D) in a relatively moist area near the north entrance, *Eupolyphaga hanae* Qiu, Che & Wang, 2018 (Fig. 4F) in drier zones, as well as bats, crickets, pseudoscorpions (Fig. 4E) and spiders. Historical cliff carvings, mostly Ming Dynasty seal scripts, are found on the walls near the entrance, and the cave has been a county-level protected cultural relic since 1982.

FIGURE 3. Habitus of *Jujiroa* spp.: **A** *J. iolandae*, Beibei, Chongqing **B** *J. kusha*, Nanjiang, Sichuan; scale bar = 1.0 mm.

Jujiroa iolandae Vigna Taglianti, 1995 约氏穴胫步甲

Figs 2F–I, 3A

Vigna Taglianti 1995: 180.

Examined materials. 1♀ (CNU), labeled: “Near Ganlong Cave, Tianqiao Village, Liuyin Town, Beibei District, Chongqing [重庆市北碚区柳荫镇天桥村干龙洞附近], 29.98383111°N, 106.5723920686°E, h=686m, 2024.6.22, leg. Yu-Zhe Chen”; 1♂ (CNU), labeled: “Near Ganlong Cave, Tianqiao Village, Liuyin Town, Beibei District, Chongqing [重庆市北碚区柳荫镇天桥村干龙洞附近], 29.98383111°N, 106.5723920686°E, h=686m, 2025.2.9, leg. Tian-Xuan Gu & Yong Zhou”; 1♀ (CJCZ), labeled: “Shenlong Cave, Qili Township, Xuanhan County, Dazhou City, Sichuan [四川省达州市宣汉县七里乡神龙洞], 2024.4.5.”

Supplemental description. *Elytra*. Interval 3 with two or three setigerous pores (Fig. 3A).

Male genitalia. Median lobe of aedeagus moderately slender and curved in lateral view (Fig. 2F), apical portion slightly curved to left side in dorsal view (Fig. 2I); apical lamella long, AL/AW 1.60, with tip sharp in lateral view, narrowly rounded in dorsal view (Fig. 2I). Right paramere narrow than left paramere, apex rounded.

Distribution. China: Sichuan and Chongqing (new record). This species is originally recorded in Liujia Cave in Tianchi Town, Huaying City, herein we reported a second locality of the same species, a nameless cave near Ganlong Cave in Tianqiao Village, Liuyin Town (Figs 5A, C, D), which is located on the other side of Huaying Mountains and is about 30 km distant to the southwest in a beeline from Liujia Cave (Fig. 6).

Remarks. The specimens from Chongqing show minor difference in the pronotal base being generally wider. However, all other characters agree with the original description. We consider this difference to fall within the range of intraspecific variation and therefore identify the specimens as conspecific.

FIGURE 4. Pangpo Cave: **A** entrance **B** exit **C** the gravel pile where the *J. danxue* sp. n. was collected **D** *Epanerchodus* sp. **E** Pseudoscorpion **F** *Eupolyphaga hanae* Qiu, Che & Wang, 2018.

***Jujiroa kusha* Jiang, Zeng, Xue & Ma, 2026 哭砂穴胫步甲**

Figs 2E, 3B

Jiang *et al.* 2026: 2.

Examined materials. 1♀ (CYZH), labeled: “Sichuan, Bazhong, Nanjiang County, Guangwushan Town, Mt. Micang, near 090 Township Road [四川省巴中市南江县光雾山镇米仓山 090 乡道附近], 32.68578650°N, 106.93567563°E, h=1584m, 2024.6.24. leg. Maozhou Xu”; 1♀ (CBFU), labeled: “Sichuan, Bazhong, Nanjiang County, Guangwushan Town, Mt. Micang, near road at night [四川省巴中市南江县光雾山镇米仓山公路旁], 32.6803°N, 106.9475°E, h=1482m, 2022.7.28. leg. Jiaheng Chen & Zechuan Li”; 1♂1♀ (CNU), labeled: “Mt. Micang, Guangwushan Town, Nanjiang County, Bazhong City, Sichuan [四川省巴中市南江县光雾山镇米仓山], at night, 32.7113°N, 106.8911°E, h=1361m, 2024.8.15, leg. Yong Zhou”.

Supplemental description. Elytra. Interval 3 with two or three setigerous pores (Fig. 3B).

Female genitalia. (Fig. 2E) Gonocoxite 1 of ovipositor with six to eight fringe setae along apical margin; Gonocoxite 2 distinctly curved, with apex narrowly acute, two ensiform setae present at outer margin, two preapical nematiform setae present.

Distribution. China: Sichuan, only known from the type locality, Mt. Micang in Nanjiang County (Fig. 6).

Habitat. All examined specimens of this species were collected on the ground near rock walls at night (Figs 5B, E), suggesting it is a nocturnal species that hides in crevices during the day.

FIGURE 5. Habitats of *Jujiroa* spp.: **A** entrance of a nameless cave near Ganlong Cave, where *J. iolandae* be collected **B** habitat of *J. kusha*, but photographed by day **C** environment inside the nameless cave near Ganlong Cave **D** an active *J. iolandae* adult **E** an active *J. kusha* adult.

Remarks. *J. kusha* was recently described based on a single male specimen. Here, we report the female adults for the first time and describe its genital characters. Additionally, it is worth noting that the first setigerous pore on interval 3 can be absent in some specimens of *J. kusha*, as in the preceding species *J. iolandae*.

This species closely resembles *J. iolandae* in external morphology, particularly in their robust forebodies, distinctly explanate pronotum, bis- or trisetose elytral interval 3, and strongly mucronate elytral apices. This combination of characters distinguishes the two species from other *Jujiroa* species in Western China. However, Jiang *et al.* (2026) provided only simplified diagnosis, which made it relatively difficult to separate these two species.

Therefore, based on examination of additional material, a detailed comparison is provided here: (1) *J. kusha* has shorter antennae, reaching the apical 1/3 of elytra, whereas in *J. iolandae* they reach the apical 1/5; (2) tempora wider in *J. kusha*; (3) elytra of *J. kusha* with striae impunctate, but elytral striae finely and distinctly punctate in *J. iolandae*; (4) aedeagus of *J. kusha* with the apical lamella shorter (AL/AW 1.07) and tip blunter in lateral view, while in *J. iolandae*, the aedeagus with longer apical lamella (AL/AW 1.60) and sharper tip; (5) Gonocoxite 2 of ovipositor is also more slender, and with a narrower tip in *J. kusha*.

FIGURE 6. Distributional map of *Jujiroa* species from Chinese mainland.

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● Additional information

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Photo Gallery

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